

A Simple Method for the Determination of Cholesterol in Blood.

BY HIRENDRANATH BANERJI.

Quite recently much importance has been attested to the changes in the cholesterol content of blood in lipoid nephrosis, diabetes and chronic obstructive jaundice, especially in relation to carbohydrate metabolism. For the estimation of cholesterol in blood common methods used are those of Bloor (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1916, **24**, 227), Meyers and Wardell (*ibid.*, 1918, **36**, 147) and Leiboff (*J. Lab. Clin. Med.*, 1930, **15**, 776).

The method of Bloor and that of Meyers and Wardell require 1 c.c. of blood which can not be obtained without veni-puncture. In the technique of Meyers and Wardell for the determination of cholesterol, a loss of cholesterol occurs in the processes of breaking small lumps of plaster of Paris with glass rod, transference of the same from the porcelain crucible to an extraction thimble and removal of extraction flask to measuring vessel.

In Leiboff's method the apparatus used can not be easily improvised in a laboratory and moreover, the apparatus is cumbersome and costly.

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

Apparatus.—The extraction apparatus used in this method is represented in Fig 1. It consists of a test tube (25 × 150 mm.), the lower end of which is drawn out to form a bulb of about 4 c.c. capacity with a 5 c.c. calibration mark etched on the neck of the bulb (Fig. 2). A condenser consisting of a test tube (15 × 120 mm.) fitted with a two hole stopper, through one of which is passed a long glass tube reaching to the bottom of the test tube while through the other a short glass tube is fitted. The closed rounded end of the test tube is drawn out into a tapering one as in Fig. 3 for the quick dropping of the condensed vapour. This condenser is held in place, on top of the extraction tube (Fig. 2) by a rubber stopper. The long glass tube is connected next with a water tap for flow of water.

Method.—Oxalated blood (0.25 c. c.) is drained out from a pipette on a fat-free porous filter paper (Whatman filter paper no. 40 treated with alcohol and acetone) in the form of a rectangle (15 × 30 mm.) roughly. It is hung up in an incubator at 37° and dried. The portion of the filter paper containing the blood is cut into 8 or 10 pieces, untouched by hand, and placed carefully one above the other in the dry extraction tube. The pieces should be such that they do not pass through the narrow stem of the extraction tube. About 3 c.c. of redistilled chloroform are introduced into the tube. The condenser is then placed in and extraction carried on for 2 hours over a plate heated by a micro-burner or an electric hot plate, cold water being allowed to flow through the condenser during the period. The chloroform extract is cooled. At the end of the process the extraction tube is detached from the condenser. Filter paper pieces are then taken out by means of a long glass rod, bent at one end. Volume is made up to 5 c.c. mark with chloroform. In a test tube 5 c.c. of a 8 mg. % solution of cholesterol in redistilled chloroform are taken, acetic anhydride (2 c. c.) and pure concentrated sulphuric acid (0.1 c. c.) are added to the contents of each tube. The tubes are then fitted with rubber stoppers and gently tilted and rotated to get uniform mixing of the contents. Then they are allowed to stand for 15 minutes in a large beaker containing water in the light by which the colour is to be matched. The readings are then taken by colorimeter.

Calculation.— $\frac{S}{R} \times 0.4 \times \frac{100}{0.25} = \text{mg. of cholesterol in 100 c.c. of blood, where } S = \text{reading of standard and } R = \text{reading of the unknown.}$

The unknown is set at 16 mm. and the result is given by 10 times the reading of the standard.

A series of parallel determinations of cholesterol in blood was carried out by the method of Meyers and Wardell (*loc. cit.*) and by the author's technique. The results are given in Table I with additional parallel determination of a known amount of cholesterol in Table II. The difference is as high as 13.8 mg. and as low as 7.7 mg. per 100 c.c. (Table II). Results are expressed in mg. per 100 c.c. of blood.

TABLE I.

Sample—whole blood.

Meyers and Wardell's.	Author's.	Diff.	Meyers and Wardell's.	Author's.	Diff.
158.1	164.0	+5.9	156.3	176.8	+20.5
152.0	176.1	+24.1	152.0	174.7	+22.7
156.3	178.1	+21.8	170.8	177.6	+7.3
160.2	154.9	-5.3	168.0	178.3	+10.3
153.0	168.8	+15.8	146.2	170.1	+24.1
158.0	176.0	+8.0	192.0	199.7	+7.7
180.1	181.5	+1.4	186.2	188.4	+2.2
182.5	174.2	-8.3			

TABLE II.

Standard cholesterol solution used.

Theoretical.	Meyers and Wardell's.	Author's.	Difference	
			Meyers and Wardell's.	Author's
95.0	79.8	94.7	10.2	0.3
120.0	112.3	118.9	7.7	1.1
150.0	141.4	149.8	8.6	0.2
160.0	146.2	160.0	13.8	0.0
180.0	169.1	179.7	10.9	0.3
200.0	191.5	199.8	8.5	0.2

SUMMARY.

1. A method has been described which is much simpler than that of Leiboff and more accurate than that of Meyers and Wardell.

2. Apparatus is very simple and can be easily improved in any laboratory.

3. It requires small amount of blood.

4. The loss due to transference has been completely avoided.

5. A number of estimations can be carried out simultaneously by connecting the condensers in series.

6. Remarkable economy in the use of reagents has been effected.

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DEPARTMENT OF PHYSIOLOGY
AND BIOCHEMISTRY,
P. W. MEDICAL COLLEGE, PATNA.

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